

The key success factors of the sustainability of associative projects in the Moroccan context

Les facteurs clés de succès de la pérennisation des projets associatifs dans le contexte marocain

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Abstract

Associative entrepreneurship is growing at the international and national levels. This increase is due to a growing need which is not being met by private enterprises, public enterprises and government measures. With the rise of international economic and financial crises, citizens around the world, including in Morocco, are demanding permanent work, fighting to reduce social inequalities and fighting against precariousness and marginalization.

It is in this context that the associative entrepreneurship found its reason of being and its fulfillment. But the entrepreneurial associative activities created face several problems and risks that threaten, at given moments of their working life, the continuity of their production process. Some activities have successfully resolved problems that almost led to the permanent cessation of their activities. Others, on the other hand, have succumbed to the serious risks and difficulties encountered.

Faced with this observation, our article has set itself the main objective of identifying the factors that have played a positive role in the process of the sustainability of entrepreneurial associative activities in the Moroccan associative context. The practical study of this work has yielded important results. Several sustainability factors have been identified and categorized.

Keywords: associative entrepreneurship; perenniality; sustainability; associative projects; association.

Résumé

L'entrepreneuriat associatif prend de l'ampleur aux niveaux international et national. Ce foisonnement s'explique par un besoin croissant qui n'est satisfait ni par les entreprises privées ni par les entreprises publiques et les actions de l'Etat. Avec la montée des crises économiques et financières internationales, les citoyens, à travers le monde y compris du Maroc, demandent un travail permanent, militent pour réduire les inégalités sociales et luttent contre la précarité et la marginalisation.

C'est dans ce cadre que l'entrepreneuriat associatif a trouvé sa raison d'être et son épanouissement. Mais les activités associatives entrepreneuriales créées affrontent plusieurs risques qui menacent, à des moments donnés de leur vie active, la continuité de leur processus de production. Certaines activités ont réussi à résoudre les problèmes qui ont failli engendrer l'arrêt définitif de leurs activités. D'autres, par contre, ont succombé face aux graves risques et difficultés rencontrés.

Face à cette constatation, notre article s'est donné comme objectif principal d'identifier les facteurs ayant joué favorablement dans le processus de pérennisation des activités associatives entrepreneuriales dans le contexte associatif marocain. L'étude pratique de ce travail a permis d'obtenir des résultats importants. Plusieurs facteurs de pérennisation ont été détectés et catégorisés.

Mots clés : Entrepreneuriat associatif ; pérennité ; pérennisation ; projets associatifs ; association.

Introduction

Social entrepreneurship is gaining momentum, both internationally and domestically. Why this scale? It responds to a need that is not satisfied either by private capitalist companies (well structured) or by public companies and the economic and social actions of the state. The need consists of responding to an offer of permanent work paid with an adequate salary, capable of reducing social inequalities and eradicating poverty. The behavior of economic actors in the private sector, stimulated by a type of economic rationality,¹ is at the origin of increased unemployment, social inequalities, and poverty. States, keen to support the private sector, strengthen its competitiveness, and be deprived of financial means, have become incapable of fulfilling their role in regulating the economy and responding to the unmet social needs of the population.

In this context, social entrepreneurship has found its purpose and developed on a global scale, as well as at the national level.

Among countless examples, microcredit developed by Muhammad Yunus with the Grameen Bank, or even fair trade, has enjoyed international success. However, not all projects and activities that fall within the social entrepreneurship model have been successful. Most ran into problems that led to bankruptcy.

In Morocco, an open country, described as liberal, has not escaped this international trend. The needs in terms of job offers, reduction of social inequalities, and the fight against poverty are increasing with the underdevelopment of the national economy and the disengagement of the state². Since its application in the early 1980s, the PAS³ has marginalized the socioeconomic aspect, focusing mainly on major macroeconomic balances and the repayment of external debt. Space hates a vacuum, as physicists say:

Withdrawal of the state must be completed. At the beginning of the 1990s, Morocco recorded the proliferation of social movements⁴ and the appearance and rise of cultural and developmental associations, especially in rural villages. Thus, they respond, concretely and in a practical manner to the situation of isolation and marginalization of the population and

¹ Increase in profits through increased productivity, cost savings, intense exploitation of resources, etc.)

² This disengagement has been established since the beginning of the 1980s following the structural adjustment policy imposed by the IMF.

³ Structural Adjustment Program.

⁴ At the beginning of the 90s, social movements multiplied (Ifni, Tata, Rif, Ouarzazate etc.). Unemployment, poverty and social inequalities are evils felt by the whole of Morocco, particularly the so-called "useless" regions. In 1995, the World Bank (BM) report described the Moroccan economy as sick and in danger of a heart attack.

society. They worked and carried out income-creating projects using their own means, and some of them were able to establish direct relationships with foreign financing. Despite incredible efforts, entrepreneurial associative activities continue to face several problems and risks. The latter threatens the continuity of production processes at given times. Some activities managed to overcome difficult times and sustain their activities. Others, however, succumbed to serious risks and difficulties encountered⁵.

The success of certain social entrepreneurial projects and activities has attracted significant interest. In our opinion, it is linked to the sustainability factors of this type of activity. Our study located at the center of this concern, seeks to answer the following fundamental question:

What are the factors and how can they ensure the sustainability of entrepreneurial activities in the Moroccan association context?

The answer to this question is in two stages.

First, we focus on a bibliographic study to revisit the concepts of sustainability in relation to perennality and social entrepreneurship. Three theoretical approaches have been mobilized in this sense: social entrepreneurship, economic sociology, and the social and solidarity economy. This bibliographic study allows us to frame the meaning of social entrepreneurship and clarify the content of sustainability with regard to perennality.

Second, we used an exploratory methodology of a qualitative and additive nature to identify the key factors that play a role in the process of perpetuating entrepreneurial associative activities in the Moroccan association context.

This methodology consisted of conducting semi-structured interviews (interview guides, actors), consulting documentary material from associations, and direct observation in the field.

The collection and analysis of data were done at two levels in two stages:

A first level :

- The preliminary phase included guides, interviews, and 32 association projects.
- Appearance of the first factors that can contribute to sustainability
- The analysis is essentially inductive.

The second level :

- The analysis was more systematic.
- Establishment of a list of factors (taken from the literature combined with others from the cases studied at the 1st level of analysis)

⁵ The INDH was launched late, in 2005, to accompany, support and supervise this type of activity.

- These factors were then distributed into different categories (projects, actors, associative structures, and contexts).

The three concepts used in this study, associative entrepreneurship, perennality, and sustainability, will be clarified before presenting and analyzing the factors that favorably promote the sustainability of this specific type of economic and social activity in the Moroccan context.

1. Literature review and conceptual clarification: Associative entrepreneurship, perennality and sustainability

What is the meaning of associative entrepreneurship? What is the content of perennality and sustainability?

Associative entrepreneurship is simply the entrepreneurship applied to associations. It is at the heart of three theoretical approaches: social entrepreneurship, economic sociology and social and solidarity economy.

1.1. Associative entrepreneurship: common features and different aspects with social entrepreneurship?

In his analysis of the American economy, the famous American economist Peter Drucker declared “that we have a very healthy economy, but a very sick society.” Society has a great need for social entrepreneurship because it responds to blatant social needs. He says that it is more important than economic entrepreneurship (Bacq S. and Janssen F. 2008, p.143).

The concept of social entrepreneurship combines two terms traditionally considered contradictory: entrepreneurship and social. How can we reconcile the rationality of the company, which is intrinsically intended to make profits, and the rationality that works for social progress?

Researchers in social entrepreneurship, who are increasing in number, have highlighted the proliferation of definitions and designs. However, they confirmed the absence of a unifying paradigm in this field of research (Dees G. 1998)⁶.

Entrepreneurship has blurred the traditional boundaries between the public, private, and non-profit sectors. It is an innovative entrepreneurial practice that has given rise to hybrid (Johnson S., 2000, p. 11) business models pursuing a strategy of creating double value: social and economic value.

⁶ Quoted by Bacqet Janssen, (2008b), p. 4

At this level, we can move forward, as highlighted by Omrane and Fayolle (2006), that social entrepreneurship has a dual purpose: business creation and the response to social needs not met by the state and/or commercial sector (Omrane A.2013, p.7). Along the same lines, Mort et al. argue that social entrepreneurship is a multidimensional construct that includes the expression of entrepreneurial behavior to accomplish a social mission.

According to Sibieude (2007), the competitive advantage of social entrepreneurship lies in its human value. Indeed, conviction, commitment, mutual aid and cooperation, and sacrifice to help others constitute productive forces that are mobilized by social actors to create wealth where the state and private sector have failed.

Rousseau (2007), analyzing the practices of this type of entrepreneurship, distinguishes two characteristics: recurrence of a permanent tension between economic performance and social performance (Rival M. 2010, p. 6).

According to Martin and Osberg (2007), social entrepreneurship includes three fundamental elements.

1. The identification of a stable but unjust balance that excludes, marginalizes, or causes suffering in a group that does not have the means to transform the balance.
2. The identification of an opportunity and the development of a new social value proposed in order to challenge the balance;
3. Finally, the development of a new stable balance to alleviate the suffering of the targeted group through imitation and the creation of a stable ecosystem around the new balance to ensure a better future for the group and society.

The synthesis of the different definitions shows that the concept of “social entrepreneurship” is a hybrid business model.

1. Identifies a stable but unjust balance marginalizing or causing suffering to a group lacking the means to change this balance (Martin R. and Osberg S., 2007);
2. Adopts a strategy aimed at creating a double value: an economic value and social value (Johnson S., 2000) or, in other words, having a dual vocation: business creation and satisfaction of social needs not satisfied by the state and/or by the commercial sector (Omrane A. 2013); entrepreneurial behavior aimed at accomplishing a social mission (Mort and AL).
3. Their elevation to the rank of productive forces capable of producing wealth for marginalized groups is a competitive advantage that the state and the private sector cannot exploit (Sibieude T., 2007);

4. Presents, at the practical level, have two characteristics: the collective dimension of action and the existence of a permanent tension between economic and social performance (Rousseau F., 2007).

Related to the associative domain, social entrepreneurship has common features but also differences with entrepreneurial associative activity.

The common traits and differences between them lie in:

1. Their ability to detect unmet needs (marginalization, exclusion, poverty, unemployment, etc.) by the commercial sector and state regulation, and work to satisfy them.

2. Their hybrid activity combines the objective of social purposes with that of making a profit. Both types of entrepreneurships offer added social value. However, the difference lies in the priority given to each objective (economic value or social value). For associative entrepreneurship, profit does not exist as an end, and its purpose is completely social (Defourny, 2010).

3. Their competitive advantage comprises a set of human values. Here too, their difference occurs at the level of the hierarchy given to the valorization of these values. Unlike social entrepreneurship, associative entrepreneurship gives priority to cultural values from the community, which increases the participation of stakeholders in different activities and strengthens their social cohesion (Boncler and Valéau, 2011);

4. Their actions integrate volunteering into a form of work. However, the concept of social entrepreneurship does not really consider the activist dimension of associations (Valéau, Cimper and Fillion, 2004) which is essentially based on volunteering.

The concept of social entrepreneurship sheds light on associative entrepreneurship. However, this does not encompass this. Notable differences were observed. Social entrepreneurship is oriented towards economic entrepreneurship and focuses on technical and economic aspects. On the other hand, associative entrepreneurship focuses more on social purposes and better integrates questions on values and ethics.

1.2. Associative entrepreneurship: what contributions does economic sociology make?

Divergences in social entrepreneurship can be bridged by recourse to the contributions of economic sociology. This theoretical foundation makes it possible to position entrepreneurial associative activities in social action and the economy.

Associative activities, primarily devoted to social action, suffer from financial insecurity. Therefore, they must manage their survival. To do this, they turned towards economic activities.

This evolution towards economic activity presents four major disadvantages (Grand Claudon-Leblan and Leblanc, 2001).

The first and important drawback concerns the gradual shift in association governance from volunteers to professionals and from elected leaders to salaried executives. The Associative specificity based on the balance between volunteering and salaried work risks disappears and consequently distorts associative entrepreneurship. The shift towards economic logic risks modifies the balance of power within associations.

The second disadvantage concerns the shift towards managerial logic imposed by market constraints (increasing one's productivity and share of activity, achieving balance in the budget, achieving and increasing profits, etc.).

The third disadvantage concerns the financial risks that economic activity can pose to an association. This risk is higher, because the association is devoid of capital.

The fourth disadvantage relates to the shift towards a field that does not correspond to the essential mission of the association: the commercial sector. The absence of a specific structure to deal with the correspondence between non-profit and commercial increases the risk of associations drifting towards this field.

1.3. Associative entrepreneurship: with regard to the social and solidarity economy?

The social and solidarity economy specifies the activities and organizations that fall within its field of analysis, according to four approaches (D'Amours, (1997); Comeau & all, (2001)).

- The first approach (Desroches, 1976) retains the fundamental components (cooperatives, mutuels, and associations for economic activities) and peripheral components of the social economy and three essential principles: the primacy of the person over capital, the equality of members, and the collective redistribution of surpluses.
- The second approach (Vienney, 1994) defines the social and solidarity economy based on a systemic vision that combines dominant actors, neglected activities, and rules. The combination of a group of people and a company linked by relationships of activity and association, maintained in coherence by the 'equality of people and collective ownership of reinvested profits.
- The third approach (Defourny and al., 1999) combines the legal institutional aspect, noting the existence of three main legal forms mutuels, cooperatives, and associations and the normative dimension based on four principles, and a fifth principle is subsequently added (Social enterprise construction, 2001).

The principles are as follows:

- The purpose of service to members or the community (rather than profit)
- Management autonomy
- Democratic decision-making processes
- The primacy of people and work over capital in the distribution of income
- Participation of members, support, and individual and collective responsibility.
- The fourth approach (Eme & Laville, 2005) positions itself in relation to the salary relationship by proposing a model of socioeconomic and political regulation. This vision emphasizes six aspects specific to societal and solidarity.
- The interweaving of a community dynamics and secondary sociality
- Reciprocity from the production of solidarity
- The compromise between various modes of coordination (market, non-market and non-monetary)
- Hybridization of resources
- Equal access to local public spaces
- Finally, the democratization of the economy is based on citizen commitment.

The solidarity economy trend sheds multiple lights on associative entrepreneurship. It offers specific elements with at least four dimensions.

- Specific elements inherent in the organizational dimension are the permanent presence of tensions within hybrid structures, combining within them a socio-community dynamic and entrepreneurial logic. These forms of organization are also present in associative entrepreneurship. These are crossed by contradictory forces. Centrifugal forces seek coherence and balance in the organizational system. They constantly oppose the forces of a centripetal nature that weakens the dynamic due to the risks of predominance of the entrepreneurial component over the socio-community component (Soulama, S., and J-B. Zett, 2002). A problem still remains regarding how to organize ourselves to manage the difficult balance between social profitability and economic viability.
- Specific elements relating to the socio-economic dimension give a place to the associative entrepreneurial activities in relation to other modes of economic production, namely, market enterprises, public enterprises, and domestic enterprises.

Associative entrepreneurship occupies a specific and notable place among these three modes of production. It has established itself as an actor in the production/distribution system of goods

and services with the priority aim of promoting the self-promotion of members and/or the promotion of its clientele or territorial community.

- Specific elements linked to the sociopolitical dimension elevate associative entrepreneurship to the rank of a political actor actively participating in local public life and territorial governance. These social actions, grouping and training of individuals, collective management, etc., contribute to the democratization of public space as a lever for participatory democracy. Its roots in civil society allow it to transition from the private to the public sphere (*Habermas, J. 1987*).

- Specific elements of interest in the socio-territorial dimension make associative entrepreneurship a capital resource that dynamically interacts with the territory of establishment. Through its organizational, socio-economic, and socio-political dimensions, associative entrepreneurship integrates into the host territory and draws from its natural resources and local know-how and values to innovate and build its competitive advantage, allowing it to ensure its survival. The territory is being built and restructured through various social, economic, and political actions developed within the framework of associative entrepreneurship.

2. Perenniality: a complex and polysemous concept

At the semantic level, sustainability is the “character of that which lasts always or for a very long time.” This content evokes a sense of sustainability, perpetuity, and longevity in projects and activities.

Using social and economic activities, we identified 14 main definitions. These were proposed between 1985 and 2009 by authors from various disciplines. We grouped this according to the following three approaches⁷:

- Achievement and sustainability of results (benefits) (Honadle and Van Sant (1985); World Health Organization (WHO) (2007)
- Survival capacities through the introduction of innovations and institutionalization of changes (Goodman et al. (1987, 1993); Rissel and Shediak-Rizkallah & al. (1995,1998);
- Absorption, reproduction and survival capacity of the community (or social structure) carrying out the activities (projects) (definitions from Goodman RM and Steckler AB (1987), Naylor & al. and Hawe & al. (1997 & 2002), May, C. and Finch, T (2009));

⁷ See appendix Table n°1.

- Multidimensional sustainability (Ducroux (2001) which advances three dimensions, Lefevre P. et al (2005) which advances 5 dimensions).

Different approaches to the concept of perennality of projects and associative activities were taken up and analyzed by Ridde and al. (2006, 2007). They concluded that perennality is the result of a “freeze frame.” It is defined on the basis of its temporal dimensions. This static concept is the observation of facts at a specific moment.

It does not integrate the dynamics that make an activity, a structure, and a result that continues to exist after a certain number of years. Ridde and al. (2006, 2007) evoke the notion of sustainability. Perennality is, in fact, the fruit of the long process of sustainability.

What is sustainability?

3. Sustainability: a dynamic, continuous concept closely linked to the concept of perennality

Sustainability is rarely used in the field of entrepreneurship. It is slightly more widespread in international cooperation and public health.

Of the six definitions of sustainability formulated⁸ between 2005 and 2007, we noted at least four common features:

- Sustainability is not perennial.
- Sustainability is closely linked to perennality.
- Sustainability is a dynamic, continuous process.
- Sustainability designates the result of a certain number of actions undertaken with the aim of perpetuating a project, activity, result, institution, etc.

Our efforts intervene at this level. This involves proposing a single definition that integrates perennality as defined by the main previous approaches, and sustainability as a dynamic and continuous process of a certain number of actions undertaken by the actors intervening within the framework of entrepreneurial associative activities. Thus, we can say that sustainability is a set of actions undertaken by the main actors of projects or entrepreneurial associative activities with the aim of ensuring the continuity of activities, of improving the absorption capacity of these activities by the supporting community (social structure), and to strengthen the contribution of the community, via institutions, to the various associative activities and to increase the satisfaction of the social structure subject to these activities.

⁸ See appendix Table n°2

When we discuss the actions taken, we ask ourselves the following question: What should we act on? This action was carried out, on a set of factors. Hence, the question is: what are the main factors on which we must act to perpetuate entrepreneurial associative activities?

4. Synthesis of results and discussion

The search for the sustainability of the creation of social value for the participating community requires the sustainability of income-generating economic activities and the continuity of donations and subsidies.

Associative projects have become a political and socioeconomic issue. There is multiple interest in the question of sustainability. However, the literature only provides only very fragmentary answers to this subject. Asking about the question of the sustainability of associative entrepreneurship requires research, among entrepreneurial associations, of the factors on which the actors act to ensure the sustainability of their activities.

The research question thus emerged by adopting an abductive methodology. To bring out this phenomenon, we have chosen to use personal experience (Fisher and al., 2021), that is, the appropriation of a research field. This approach also refers to the concept of “pre-understanding” (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2022), intended to consider the researcher's prior knowledge of a subject. This empirical managerial observation made it possible to establish an inductive starting point for the first abduction loop. The second abduction loop consists of a case study carried out with 19 associations carrying out social actions with diversified activities⁹ and falling within the framework of associative entrepreneurship in the Errachidia region in Morocco. Their associative projects carried out by them seek to meet the social needs of the community and present entrepreneurial aspects. Semi-structured interviews were also conducted. Thus, we conducted qualitative research on an exploratory nature.

This research allowed the detection of a large number of factors. We grouped them into three homogeneous categories of factors: those linked to the project, those linked to actors, and those related to the context.

⁹ In particular, these are the following activities to promote local oasis products in the agricultural and artisanal fields: Purchase of D'man sheep, Workshop for sewing and women's work, Construction of a socio-cultural complex, Acquisition of a micro-oil mill unit, Development of local date products, Completion of construction of a tourist lodge, Breeding of the D'man sheep breed, Development of oasis products (purchase of equipment and supplies for traditional couscous preparation and grinding and packaging henna), Creation of a women's group for cow breeding, Fattening of bull calves, Economic integration program, Construction and equipment of a collective laundry with a gray water purification system, Creation of a date production and valorization unit, Valorization of the oasis product (creation of units for the production of apple juice), Creation of units for the processing of dates, Workshop for manual embroidery and sewing work, Equipment for the production and marketing of couscous, Creation of a unit for the preparation of date legs, Qualification of artisan jewelers.

4.1. Nine sustainability factors linked to the project and its hybrid structure

The study of the factors linked to the project and its hybrid structure shows the existence of two groups of factors: those linked to the project and those related to its social structure.

From the reading of the factors linked to the project, we have retained three important factors that must be taken into consideration to ensure the sustainability of a project related to associative entrepreneurship:

- The relevance of the project: The project must meet a social need (a useful social value) and an economic need (economic value); these needs must be correctly identified, strongly felt by the community, and long-term.
- The project must be well designed: clarification of the objectives, forecasting of the financial means and resources to be exploited, and designing a way to get buy in the community targeted by the project.
- Objectively evaluate human skills, know-how, and human values to be put forward to mobilize members and the target population.

The main factors linked to the hybrid structure of the project are also four:

- The ability to balance the legal framework governing associations considered rigid and the flexibility sought by associations in terms of research and benefit sharing.
- Managing permanent tensions between the social purpose of the project (its reason for being) and that of making profits (means of continuing to offer these social services).
- The capacity for innovation to establish specific governance and organization combining participatory and democratic management (to satisfy and encourage the social base to adhere to the project) and leadership compatible with entrepreneurial logic (speed of decision making and rapid reactions).
- Ability to manage tensions between volunteering (unpaid work) and salaried work (paid work).

In our opinion, these are the nine main factors for implementing an associative project over a long period. These factors directly influence the possibilities of appropriation of the project by the actors (activists and target population), on its relevance, on the capacity to convince public authorities and donors to contribute to the financing of the project, and consequently on the possibilities to make it perennial.

4.2. Five sustainability factors linked to actors and their skills

The project stakeholders were grouped into three types. Project leaders or activists (instigators), community members targeted by the project, and external stakeholders (institutions: DAS,

INDH, international cooperation, etc.). We distinguished the sustainability factors of interest into the first and second types of actors.

Sustainability factors are linked to the first and second types of actors. According to our assessment, the most important are those that concern the strengthening of the skills and competencies of the actors directly linked to the project (project leaders and interested communities). There are five factors involved:

- The intensity of the commitment and the capacity for sacrifice of the project activists, who must be bearers of ideals and values of change and convinced of the success of their project.
- The capacity of the leading actors to manage conflicts of interest for the benefit of the interest of the community and to develop the culture of compromise, sharing of responsibility, and collective participation in decision-making;
- Awareness and collective conviction that the link between responsibility, control, and accountability is a guarantee of sustainability
- Acquisition of basic training at this level
 - Technical: management tools, project management, and business governance
 - Politics: capacity for mobilization and supervision of the interested community
 - Relational and formation of networks with institutions and local leaders.
- The ability to reconcile democratic and participatory governance and the essential place of leadership capable of concentrating efforts on the permanent management of tensions linked to the search for a difficult balance between entrepreneurial dynamics and the associative components of projects.

Strengthening the skills and abilities of stakeholders certainly contributes to the sustainability of associative entrepreneurship.

4.3. Sustainability factors inherent to the context and environment

The environment in which the project was implemented is diverse. It contains the potential and resources to exploit and constraints and handicaps to avoid. The knowledge and consideration of this reality can contribute to the sustainability of associative entrepreneurship. We distinguished three groups of factors linked to the context and environment of the associative project: political and legal factors, socio-cultural factors, and territorial factors.

There are four main factors linked to the political and legal context that can unfavorably influence associative entrepreneurship:

- Totally centralized decision-making power
- The absence of local political will.

- The desire of local leaders to submit the activists of the project to their political tendency and seek to monetize this membership.

- The incapacity of the legal and regulatory framework governing the associations to intervene quickly to resolve possible conflicts that may arise between interested parties.

There are several sociocultural factors. Certain human values of the populations and certain Moroccan customary laws, such as “Tawiza”, commitment, patience, assiduity, respect and the sacredness of decisions, the spirit of collaboration, sacrifice, punishment by fines, etc., can be mobilized and exploited within the framework of associative work. They constitute intangible capital capable of contributing favorably to supervision and mobilization for the production of social and economic values by and for the community.

Multiple factors are linked to territorial anchoring. Associative entrepreneurship interacts with territory where it is established. The territory offers associative entrepreneurship natural resources, local knowledge, positive ancestral values, and customs to produce goods and services by and for the community. Associative entrepreneurship improves the professional situation of populations through methods of learning self-promotion, development education, and active citizenship. These actions of associative entrepreneurship contribute to the construction and development of the territory. Anchoring associative entrepreneurship with in a territory is a requirement for sustainability.

Conclusion

In short, this categorization of factors for the sustainability of entrepreneurial projects in the Moroccan associative context can only truly contribute to their sustainability when they are integrated without restriction into the different dimensions of the projects and with a combined will of all stakeholders within a convergence of socio-economic policies.

A certain number of constraints and shortcomings hinder the timely realization of certain associative projects and threaten their perennality, signaling constraints relating to the financing problem, entrepreneurial shift, problems of associative governance, use of entrepreneurial tools, qualification of human resources, and marketing of products.

All this leads us to conclude that the use of more entrepreneurial and effective management and organizational tools around these associative projects is necessary to guarantee their sustainability. However, if this recourse does not go as far as appropriation and institutionalization, the chances of perpetuating achievements are limited.

The spontaneous nature of such a process in a context marked by the absence of an institutional framework of reference and the fact that investment in the entrepreneurial field by associations

remains more subject to the logic of learning on the job and experimentation with modes of operation and organization than to the logic of management professionals. This explains the difficulties encountered by these associations in ensuring coherent and balanced organizational governance with a view to aligning their social base with entrepreneurial logic.

The difficulty of maintaining the balance between the entrepreneurial dynamic and the associative component of projects shows the essential role of associative and institutional leadership in this process. The perceived intentions record a gap between those of institutional actors, generally very focused on socio-political and traceability aspects, and those of the other associative and beneficiary actors, the most numerous, for whom short-term economic interest takes more importance of space.

Ultimately, the entire sustainability process can find its full justification and provide proof of its success.

APPENDICES

Table 1: Definitions of the concept perennality

Authors	Year	Definition	Dimensions and characteristics
Honadle G.H. & Van Sant J	1985	perennality is defined as the continuity of benefits.	Results and ongoing effects
Goodman R.M. & Steckler A. B	1987	perennality is seen as the capacity of institutions to survive	Survival of supporting structures
Goodman & al.	1993	Perennality represents the capacity of institutions to introduce innovations and institutionalize changes	Introduce innovations and institutionalize changes
Rissel et Shediac-Rizkallah & al.	1995 1998	Call it institutionalization	
Naylor & al. Et Hawe & al.	1997 Et 2002	Define perennality when program components and activities are adopted and absorbed by the community.	Some authors introduce the notion of competent community

Ducroux	2001	Perenniality consists of institutions committing their actions over time	Characteristics: sustainability Three dimensions: financial autonomy, institutional and social viability, as well as technical efficiency.
Wootton, R. & Hebert, M.A	2001	Qualify a program as having perenniality when it continues to operate after the pilot project phase.	perenniality is often defined according to its temporal dimension, i.e. its longevity.
Naylor & al.	2002	Define a project as perennial when project components and activities are absorbed into the routine activities of community organizations	Activities become routine within the structure
Lefevre P. & al.	2005	Personality can be defined as the quality of a device, a system, a structure, a service, a product, a result, a benefit or an effect which long-term	Five dimensions: The functionality of the device; Financial viability; Institutional viability; The integration of innovation; Improving and maintaining the quality of services. Characteristic of sustainability over time.
Guide to Good Practices for	2005	Perenniality is the "character of that which lasts forever or for a very long time	Characteristics of durability and perpetuity.

sustaining a health innovation			
Ridde V. & al.	2006	It is the result of the process, it is a “freeze frame” of sustainability.	
Ridde, V. & al.	2007	Perenniality is defined as being the result of the sustainability process at a given time; it corresponds to a sort of "freeze image".	The four characteristics of routines are: memory, adaptation, values and rules. The presence of organizational routines makes it possible to assess the degree of perenniality
World Health Organization (WHO)	2007	Character of that which lasts always or for a very long time, a word which has gradually taken on the meaning of lasting, perpetual.	Actions can be qualified as perennial when they are able to provide an appropriate level of benefits (quality, quantity, greater convenience, comfort, business continuity, affordability, efficiency, equity, reliability) and have the capacity to continue beyond the life cycle of the invested resources.
May, C. & Finch, T	2009	Perenniality exists when the practices that develop are reproduced and end up becoming part of the social structure of the organization	Perenniality is more likely when the program becomes institutionalized and there is standardization

Table 2 : Definitions of sustainability

Authors	Year	Definition of sustainability	Dimensions and characteristics
Lefevre P. et al.	2005	Sustainability is defined as the dynamic process of inscription in the duration of the object (production, result, etc.) that we wish to make perennial and which leads to perennality.	Characteristics: dynamic, sustainable and sustained Sustainability can be spontaneous, naturally or on the contrary planned, organized
Guide to Good Practices for sustaining a health innovation	2005	Sustainability is a dynamic process, it is therefore more the capacity to adapt of a structure which is more decisive for personality than the balance of humanity, structural and financial resources.	Dynamism, adaptation
Ridde V. & al.	2006	Sustainability concerns the future of programs and is centered on the process which allows the continuation of activities and effects relating to programs.	This is the result of the Project. The continuation of activities and effects. Evaluation in a Transversal manner, at any time and punctuality
Ridde V. & al.	2007	Sustainability is defined as the continuation of the effects and activities of programs and projects. This process begins from the first events that mark the progress of the projects.	The timing of the project is not the time of sustainability. The dimension of continuity of effects and activities

World Health Organization (WHO)	2007	Perenniality is the action of perpetuating. It designates both the character of what lasts and the action to be carried out to achieve it. Sustainability is a process requiring a combination of different factors which includes the essential elements of the project and those of its implementation.	Sustainability and action
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ABBREVIATIONS

Sigles	Designations
AIMS	International Association of Strategic Management
BM	World Bank
DAS	Social Action Division
IMF	International Monetary Fund
INDH	National Humain Development Initiative
INSPQ	National Institute of Public Health of Quebec
PAS	Structural Adjustment Program
WHO	World Health Organization

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